

SOCIABILITY IN THE FORMATION OF EMOTIONAL AND VOLITIONAL QUALITIES IN MILITARY PERSONNEL.

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Annotatsiya

Harbiy xizmat davomida insonga zarur bo'lgan hissiy-irodaviy sifatlar boriki, shunday sifatalarsiz inson iroda, tashabbuskorlik va jasorat, qat'iyat va maqsadlilik kabi insoniy fazilatlargacha harbiy xizmatchi shaxsi shakllanmaydi. Sababi faoliyati davomida harbiy xizmat talablari shunday fazilatlarini taqazo qiladi. Quyidagi maqolada ayni shunday sifatning harbiy xizmat davomida zarurati, shakllanish mexanizmlari va rivojlantirish tamoyillari haqida to'xtalamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: hissiy-irodaviy barqarorlik, maqsadlilik, qat'iylik, intizom, tashabbus, jasorat.

Аннотация

Есть эмоционально-волевые качества, которые необходимы человеку во время военной службы, без таких качеств, как воля, инициатива и мужество, решительность и целеустремленность, личность военнослужащего не формируется. Причина в том, что требования военной службы во время карьеры диктуют такие качества. В следующей статье мы остановимся именно на необходимости таких качеств во время военной службы, механизмах формирования и принципах развития.

Ключевые слова: эмоционально-волевая устойчивость, целеустремленность, настойчивость, дисциплина, инициатива, мужество.

Annotation

There are emotional and volitional qualities that are necessary for a person during military service, without such qualities as will, initiative and courage, determination and determination, the personality of a serviceman is not formed. The reason is that the requirements of military service during a career dictate such qualities. In the next article, we will focus specifically on the need for such qualities during military service, the mechanisms of formation and the principles of development.

Keywords: emotional and volitional stability, determination, perseverance, discipline, initiative, courage.

Introduction and relevance of the topic. The solution to the problem of experiences, feelings, States of a person is associated with a determining function in relation to almost all areas of their existence (development, communication, relationship, activity, implementation of values). The ability of a person to control his own behavior, to mobilize his strength to overcome difficulties is a condition associated with the quality of will.

In this article, we turned to the consideration of the axamyat of communication in the formation of emotional - volitional qualities in the context of military service, but at the

beginning we need to highlight a number of general points. In mental activity, the will performs two interconnected functions: activating and controlling.

The physiological basis of voluntary movement is the interaction of the first and second signal systems as a result of their influence and with the leading role of the second signal system.

A simple voluntary action consists of two branches: the motivation for the action aimed at the goal, which is more or less clearly carried out, and the immediate action, which is carried out immediately.

Complex voluntary movement involves three stages: preparatory, basic, final.

Emotional-volitional stability is the level of voluntary control of a person's sufficiently strong emotions. It acts as a structural complex of actions and actions of the individual and the brave and courageous in battle. Being emotionally stable means that you have inner strength to resist the challenges of your life, and you maintain peace even when your life seems to be the most chaotic. "Emotional stability is a desirable trait. This means that you can cope with difficult situations, overcome difficulties and be productive and capable," says neurologist and writer Nicole. Psychologist Arthur E. Poropat explains that "more emotionally stable people are more vulnerable to negative stimuli and therefore less depressed, less distracted and more confident in their abilities". In fact, research shows that there is a direct relationship between emotional stability and confidence in maintaining balance.

The purposeful process of conscious action, which is set to overcome various types of difficulties and achieve it, is carried out by willpower. With the help of the will of a person, he organizes his activities and controls his behavior. Willpower can affect things big and small. Will always manifests itself in a person's daily life, but it clearly manifests itself in especially complex and responsible situations.

Experience. Where does will come from in a person, what are its psychological mechanisms, if we look for answers to questions like. Like the entire human psyche, will is primarily a function of a person and his brain. Will movement is the result of the interaction of the first and second signaling systems. This is exactly what forms the physiological basis of all voluntary human behavior. The leading role in this case belongs to the second signaling system.

A person is born with strong and weak will. It is formed and develops in the process of Labor. Ordinary labor activity also requires the presence of Labor qualities and their targeted formation. Consequently, the specificity of the volitional psychological process consists in a non-conscious act aimed at activating all the forces and capabilities of a particular person in order to achieve the goal. In these movements, individuals distinguish between simple and complex voluntary movements:

1. A simple act of will consists of two stages: motivation to action and the act itself.
2. A complex will movement consists of several stages:
 - a) preparation - during this period, motivation and goal setting occur; awareness of a number of possibilities for achieving the goal; the emergence of motives and their struggle; the final choice of the motive of action and the determination of ways to achieve the goals.
 - b) the stage of practical action is the implementation of the decision made.
 - c) the final stage is characterized by the generalization of the work performed, the analysis of positive and negative motives in the work, the accumulation of experience.

A particularly complex volitional action is carried out in an extremely short time, mobilizing all the forces of the individual. Speaking about Will, we emphasized the conditions for its development-the need to constantly overcome something, to fight some kind of difficulties. When overcoming them, qualities that characterize will are formed. There are a lot of such strong-willed qualities, but let's consider some of them that have a special significance in military activities.

1. Purposefulness is a quality that expresses the ability of a warrior to subordinate and follow his actions to certain goals.

2. Assertiveness is a quality that expresses an individual's ability to make informed decisions in a timely manner and engage in their implementation without personal delay.

Discipline is a quality that expresses the ability of an individual to strictly and correctly comply with the requirements of laws, moral standards and values of society. Discipline-these are the requirements and the degree of assimilation by a person, which has become the quality of their observance. Self-control is quality. Expression of the ability to limit physical and psychological activity that interferes with achieving the goal. Calmness is self-control that usually manifests itself in a difficult situation, especially in battle. Self-control requires self-control-the inability of a person to behave in difficult conditions. This is the reason for all disputes, the necessary condition for the loss of power. Initiative is a quality that reveals the ability and ability of an individual to show creativity and independence in the performance of tasks. Human initiative to resist rudeness, inertia, and loquacity.

Courage is a quality that characterizes the ability of a fighter to perform new and difficult tasks, the result of which is not always clear, for example: to start an attack (they can kill), to take responsibility and show courage, to resist cowardice - no matter what.

Courage is a quality that expresses a person's ability to complete a task in conditions that immediately endanger his life.

It is a virtue that reveals the ability of a person not to lose his intelligence and to behave with respect and honor in any situation, even in a fatal one courage.

Quality that expresses a person's ability to show moral and physical endurance and good mood is endurance. Perseverance is manifested only in the fight against difficulties.

Energy and perseverance are qualities that reveal a person's ability to direct energy for a long time and without reduction. Hard work is a quality that expresses an individual's ability to perform activity, diligence, instructions, commands, etc.systematically and on time. Independence is a quality that reveals a person's ability to believe in one's own ability, critically assess what is achieved, and take responsibility for the decision made. These and other qualities are in the relationship, complement and act on each other.

Together, these qualities characterize the strong will of a person. The warrior, first of all, needs a strong will to successfully solve combat tasks. The fact is that it is combat actions that include various factors that negatively affect the will of a person. The danger, as mentioned above, can lead to illness, fear, confusion. In order to successfully complete a combat mission, effectively use equipment and military weapons, and control their behavior, the fighter must suppress negative emotions.

Methodological recommendations. Methods for the formation of emotional-volitional stability:

- strengthening positive motives for active and targeted activities in a difficult situation;
- to gain regular experience in behavior and task performance in harsh conditions;

- activate the desire to be persistent, brave, brave, etc.;
- to create an atmosphere of behavior in harsh conditions in a military community.

How to form a strong will in a warrior? What are the ways to do this? Under what conditions does the formation of will occur faster? Building confidence in the correctness of his work and unconditional victory (for example: A. Matrosov, N. Gastello). Worldview and belief are the basis of moral and Educational will:

- development of political consciousness of cadets;
- gathering experience of volitional behavior;
- ensuring continuity of difficulties and their gradual increase make it possible to strengthen the will;
- taking into account psychological difficulties and personal characteristics, educating his strong-willed qualities;
- self-knowledge of the fighters themselves. Because this is where self-education begins.

But knowledge must be honest:

- what is positive and what is negative. On this basis, a plan is drawn up for independent work on oneself;
- use of the team to develop strong-willed qualities;
- to create an environment in which there is danger and danger.

The upbringing of the Will is carried out on the basis of the direction of the individual, the formation of a system of high motives and fighters.

The formation of a deep, directed belief is decisive. We must act in such a way that a sense of duty, responsibility, collectivism and other high spiritual and martial qualities are inherent in every warrior.

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